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D1.2 - DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

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PROJECT ACRONYM:	FoodCLIC
PROJECT NUMBER:	101060717
WORK PACKAGE NUMBER AND TITLE:	WP1 - Developing methodological, training and monitoring frameworks
LEAD BENEFICIARY:	ULisboa-FM
WORK PACKAGE LEADER:	VU
RELEVANT TASK:	1.5 - Development of data management plan and shielded data-sharing platform for cross-city-region learning (M2-54)
DISSEMINATION LEVEL:	PU – Public
DUE DATE (MONTH):	M5 (Deliverable was submitted in the EU portal in M5, resubmitted in the new FoodCLIC template in M10)
VERSION:	1.1

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION	5
2. DATA SUMMARY	6
2.1 Re-use of existing data.....	6
2.2 Project generated data.....	6
2.3 Expected size of data.....	7
2.4 Data utility	7
3. FAIR DATA	7
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	7
3.2 Making data openly accessible.....	8
3.3 Making data interoperable.....	10
3.4 Increasing data re-use.....	10
3.5 Data quality assurance processes	10
4. OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS	11
5. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES.....	12
6. DATA SECURITY.....	12
7. ETHICS	13
8. OTHER ISSUES.....	14

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1	Types of data generated during FoodCLIC	12
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1. INTRODUCTION

This document provides the FoodCLIC Data Management Plan (DMP) to be first delivered in Month 5 and updated periodically, according to the Description of Action of the project. The regular updates will be conducted by the Executive Board (EB) supervised by the Coordinator, throughout the project timeline, whenever relevant changes arise. Relevant changes include new data types, changes in consortium policies, consortium composition, or any external factors that may impact data protection, processing, or sharing protocols. Notwithstanding, updates are mainly expected in Months 18 and 36.

The DMP outlines what kind of data will be collected or generated and how it will be handled, processed, and shared. It describes the standards that will be incorporated and the related methods for data collection, processing, and data sharing. This deliverable is based on the template and guidelines provided by the European Commission for data management plans¹.

FoodCLIC aims to build strong science-policy-practice interfaces to develop evidence-based and integrated food policies and render food-sensitive planning frameworks, creating more progressive and resilient urban food environments and aiming to empower citizens (particularly from deprived and vulnerable groups) to access, afford, and choose healthier and more sustainable foods.

To achieve the projects' aim, the Food Policy Networks (FPNs), through their Living Labs, will initially operate based on a collective understanding of the city-region food system, a shared vision for the urban food environment, as well as of sociodemographic and health profiles of exposed populations, and jointly performed analyses of good practices. Informed by this knowledge base, FPNs will formulate an integrated food strategy to make healthy and sustainable food the easy choice for all. This food strategy will act as a source of inspiration to attract more stakeholders to the FPN, and to steer subsequent learning from real-life interventions in the Living Labs, the development of evidence-based and integrated urban food policies, and food-sensitive planning frameworks by municipalities and other relevant organizations. In addition to realizing actual changes in food environments, real-life interventions will help to uncover barriers to, and facilitators of, scaling processes and to identify innovative business models, investment schemes, conducive market conditions, and land use plans.

¹ Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/how-to-participate/reference-documents;programCode=HORIZON>

2. DATA SUMMARY

2.1 RE-USE OF EXISTING DATA

To better understand the overall state-of-the-art as well as the contextual situation in the city regions, FoodCLIC will conduct several mapping exercises at the international and city-region/municipal levels. FoodCLIC will identify and assess food-related policies, planning frameworks, and initiatives and examples of good practices from existing initiatives in partner city-regions, in the signatory cities of the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact, from cities involved in FoodCLIC-related EU projects, statistics and other official documents from the involved municipalities, scientific and “grey” literature (e.g., reports, theses), and public registry databases (e.g., morbidity, food balance). For this, text and numerical data, images, audio, video, and geographical information will be used.

2.2 PROJECT GENERATED DATA

FoodCLIC is expected to collect or generate both quantitative and qualitative data from observations (experience/instantaneous sampling), interviews, focus groups, world cafes, Delphi panels, surveys, geographical documentary analysis, ethnography, participant observation, and documentary analysis, among other types of methodological approaches, during the mapping exercises and the designing, implementation, and evaluation of real-life interventions. Datasets, text, videos, audio, photos, geospatial information, and scripts are planned to be generated during the project.

Data will be collected using the already indicated methodological approaches, involving the general population (children, adults, and older adults), dwellers or institutionalized individuals, including deprived and vulnerable populations, stakeholders from public, private, and/or non-profit organizations, and other researchers and experts. Moreover, data collection may involve different settings (schools, elderly homes, labor settings, etc.)

The generated data, together with data that will be re-used (mentioned above), is necessary to achieve the following FoodCLIC specific objectives:

- To map urban food systems, policies, and actions and analyze good practices in terms of integration, with a special focus on urban food environments and short supply chains (WP2).
- To develop a reflexive monitoring framework and guidelines to help planners and policy-makers to understand the range of barriers to, and opportunities for, interventions that enhance urban food environments and the urban food system (WP1 and WP2).
- To develop, implement, monitor, evaluate and redevelop interventions and evidence-based integrated urban food policies and planning frameworks that realize food environments able to deliver co-benefits in terms of health, climate, circularity, inclusion, and the empowerment of communities (WP3).
- To build a pan-European knowledge base for evidence-based integrated urban food policies and food-sensitive planning frameworks, including a range of implementation actions (WP4).

2.3 EXPECTED SIZE OF DATA

Although the size of individual datasets is not expected to be very large (individual deposited files, even videos, are not expected to exceed 10 gigabytes), it is expected that the total data burden at the end of the project will be considerable. Nevertheless, it is not expected that the total burden of the existing data, together with the project-generated data, will exceed five terabytes.

2.4 DATA UTILITY

The data generated throughout the FoodCLIC project will be useful for policymakers at national, regional, and local scales, FPNs involved stakeholders and interested social actors, academics and researchers, civil organizations, and citizens.

3. FAIR DATA

3.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

Whenever possible, data generated within the project will be made available (publicly or under restricted access). This will be ensured by using the digital repository Zenodo as the unique data-sharing platform of the project.

Zenodo is a general-purpose open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and hosted by CERN. It allows researchers to deposit the final version of generated files, such as research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and any other research-related digital artifacts. Unlike cloud platforms for sharing and storing data that will be used for files that have not been finalized (namely, SharePoint via Microsoft Teams), once a record has been published to Zenodo, the files in the record can no longer be changed—only new versions can be added—becoming a permanent indexed file. This allows full traceability when data is reused by other users (e.g., researchers), as the specific version used should be referenced.

Each document, of any type, deposited in Zenodo will be assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier, specifically a digital object identifier (DOI). This will ensure that stored items will be easily citable, which is another advantage over other systems for data sharing and storage. The cost-free use of the Zenodo platform is limited to 50 gigabytes per file.

To enhance data public discovery, each uploaded record in Zenodo is described using rich metadata compliant with DataCite's Metadata Schema minimum and recommended terms. Metadata of deposited data will provide information at least about the following: datasets information (contents description, date of deposit, author(s), venue, and embargo); grant project name, acronym, and number; Horizon Europe funding; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset, authors

involved in the action, their organizations, and the grant. Keywords will also be provided to optimize the possibility for discovery and potential re-use.

The metadata of each record is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing. The metadata of each record are sent to DataCite servers during DOI registration and indexed there.

3.2 MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

About the repository

Zenodo is a well-established public repository. Therefore, no special arrangements need to be made for depositing data on this platform. The FoodCLIC community in Zenodo will be set up in Month 6, collecting all files related to the FoodCLIC project. A user manual (i.e., tutorial) specifying the procedures to upload all relevant files to the FoodCLIC community collection will be shared among the consortium partners in Month 6. From Month 7 onwards, all FoodCLIC partners should upload all relevant files (final versions) following the shared tutorial. All documents finalized before Month 7 will be uploaded to the FoodCLIC community once it is set up.

All partners of FoodCLIC endorse the compromise to deposit all re-used or generated research data in the Zenodo repository, if legal and ethical aspects allow, while fully respecting ethical and data protection principles and legislation (including the highest standards of research integrity as set out in the ALLEA European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, as well as applicable international and national laws, including the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and the European Convention on Human Rights and its Supplementary Protocols. ethical and data protection principles), also detailed in the FoodCLIC Ethics Handbook (D1.3).

It is important to highlight that Zenodo has been selected as the FoodCLIC data-sharing platform because it has a long-standing and solid user base, details terms of use, has an open access content policy, supports retention, supports backup, provides Open Access content, assigns persistent identifiers, follows metadata standards, supports mid- and long-term preservation, and has data security mechanisms in place.

About access to data

The FoodCLIC consortium will enable third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate data. Nevertheless, we anticipate generating sensitive or confidential data that cannot be openly shared or can only be shared under restricted conditions. Whenever possible, personal data will be anonymized to make it openly available when consent has been given. If not possible (e.g., data that identifies the participating organizations, or is identifiable by nature), following the EU General Data Protection Regulation, data cannot be shared through the open repository. Although individual data cannot be shared, aggregated data will be shared, whenever possible, and a systematic effort will be done by FoodCLIC partners to provide aggregated data (ensuring anonymization or, if not possible, pseudo-anonymization).

An embargo period for sharing research data can be necessary to apply, namely due to constraints in the time-to-publish results through scientific publications, theses, or dissertations. The embargo period will be as long as strictly necessary for the mentioned purposes, not exceeding 1.5 years after the project ends.

As already mentioned, Zenodo uses an open, free, and universally implementable protocol to access data. Data and metadata are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol; metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name; and metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API.

As previously mentioned, some limitations to sharing generated data are expected. For this reason, we anticipate having different levels of access, using Zenodo's protocols for authentication and authorization procedures. Access levels will include: (Level 1) full access for results and anonymized data deposited in Zenodo; (Level 2) FoodCLIC researchers-only access; and (Level 3) access under prior authorization process, specifying the purpose of consulting or using the deposited data.

Even when access is restricted, metadata are publicly accessible and licensed under public domain for all data shared in the repository. No authorization is ever necessary to retrieve this metadata information, ensuring the location and transparency of data re-used or generated throughout FoodCLIC.

About metadata

Metadata of all shared files (with or without restrictions) will be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication (Creative Commons CC0 – “No rights reserved”), as per Article 17 of the Grant Agreement. Metadata will contain access requirements, applicable to each data file, as well as detailed information about how to request access.

In Zenodo, data and metadata can be retained for the lifetime of the repository. Currently, it has an experimental program defined for the next 20 years at least. Since metadata are stored in high-availability database servers at CERN, which is separate from the data itself, metadata are accessible even when the data are no longer available (for record purposes or, if applicable, for direct-to-researcher/s contact/s about the project/data). Anyway, FoodCLIC will ensure long-term data preservation of at least 10 years in Zenodo. The above-mentioned data access committee will be responsible for this data permanency. The data management system will evolve to become an open-access metadata repository to record (post-FoodCLIC) initiatives inspired by FoodCLIC that aim to improve food environments and the wider urban food system.

Some generated data might need specific software to access or read it. In these cases, efforts will be made to include the relevant software (e.g., in open source). If not possible, popular software will be used in the data processing, to increase the chances of accessibility.

3.3 MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

Specific requirements will be defined and updated regularly by the FoodCLIC Executive Board to harmonize data from different countries and the different Living Labs involved in the project. This will maximize the possibility to integrate data, thereby increasing their analytical and interpretative power. Specifically, to share baseline and endline data from WP3, a central data cleaning and management process, and a data catalog for issuing data, will be established.

If uncommon or generated project-specific ontologies or vocabularies need to be used, mapping to more commonly used ontologies will be provided and will be openly shared to allow reusing, refining, or extending.

Where applicable, the meta(data) will include qualified references (i.e., persistent identifiers) to other (meta)data (related publications or other research outputs), as possible in Zenodo. If needed to reference external metadata, a resolvable URL will be referenced.

3.4 INCREASING DATA RE-USE

Whenever possible, documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use will be shared in Zenodo and cited in the documentation describing the results (e.g., reports, scientific publications). These include readme files with information about the data files, codebooks, data cleaning protocols, statistical syntaxes, qualitative open-coding systems, and documented outputs, among others. Data will be adequately described using the appropriate procedures available in each type of data, to allow accurate interpretation of data, including (or references to information about) the provenance of data and methods used to generate the data. Additionally, records will be accompanied by metadata describing provenance in detail.

Data will be made freely available in the public domain through the Zenodo repository. Unless limitations are required due to legal reasons (e.g., identifiable personal data, consent to share data not provided), data will be licensed under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0) or a license with equivalent rights, as laid out in the Grant Agreement. License is one of the mandatory terms in Zenodo's metadata. Thus, data produced in the project will be usable by third parties, including after the end of the project.

3.5 DATA QUALITY ASSURANCE PROCESSES

Data quality will be ensured by following the central data cleaning, management, and harmonization processes and the data catalog for issuing data established within the project by the Executive Board, as laid out in the Description of Action.

4. OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS

In addition to the research data discussed above, other research outputs are expected to be generated throughout the project. These include different documents produced as intermediate or final achievements of FoodCLIC, namely guidelines, reports, scientific manuscripts, presentations, posters, scripts, coding systems and R syntaxes/outputs, policy briefs, and media (i.e., blog posts, podcasts, news articles, etc.). Table 1 summarizes the different types of outputs expected to be generated in the different phases of the data lifecycle.

PREPARATION	GENERATED DATA	SUPPORTING ANALYSIS	REPORTING AND DISSEMINATION
Protocols Plans/guides Informed consent form Ethics committee docs	Datasets Videos Audios Photos Text Geospatial Scripts	Scripts Syntax Qualitative coding system files	Reports (deliverables) Policy briefs Flyers Videos Audios (interviews or presentations) Scientific papers Posters

Table 1: Types of data generated during FoodCLIC

When possible, research outputs will be submitted through the same protocols discussed above for research data, in line with the FAIR principles. Unless for legal reasons, the different types of documents will be shared (with or without restrictions, as necessary) as soon as possible in Zenodo, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC-BY) or Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0) or a license with equivalent rights. Data related to preparation and reporting and dissemination will also be accessible through FoodCLIC’s website (as part of the Knowledge Hub). FoodCLIC results will be published as open-access peer-reviewed scientific publications. At the latest, at the time of publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication will be deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications, ensuring that immediate open access is provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or a license with equivalent rights, as laid out in the Grant Agreement. For monographs and other long-text formats, the license may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g., CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND).

Metadata of deposited publications will be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent, in line with the FAIR principles, and provide information at least

about the following: publication (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue); Horizon Europe or Euratom funding; grant project name, acronym, and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organizations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata will include persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication, also deposited in the digital repository.

5. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

FoodCLIC data management is delegated to Task 1.5, for which ULisboa-FM is the Task Leader. Throughout the project's lifetime, all consortium partners are responsible to implement the Data Management Plan in its updated version, as per Article 6 of the Consortium Agreement.

Long-term data preservation of at least 10 years is ensured by opting for free-of-charge data storage. Indeed, and as already mentioned, the Zenodo repository offers a 20-year operation (or longer), thus, securing long-term preservation. FOODCLIC's internal data-sharing platform will partly be duplicated in an open-access metadata repository of initiatives aiming to promote changes in the urban food environment and the wider urban food system – the Knowledge Hub – under the responsibility of WP5. Long-term preservation of data will be covered by VU.

For open-access publication, the project's funding has allocated 6,000€ for each research partner.

6. DATA SECURITY

The FoodCLIC project will be compliant with the data protection legislation of member countries and the EU General Data Protection Regulation.

Personal data will only be collected where necessary and after collection of informed consent, and all personal data will be held securely by the relevant partner, will be treated confidentially, and handled following EU General Data Protection Regulation legislation, including individuals having the right to amend or remove personal data before anonymization. Identifiable data will be rendered irreversibly anonymous wherever practicable. Where not possible, stringent measures concerning data protection will be taken, such as security of records, encryption, coding, use of pseudonyms, or removal of identifying contextual information, according to data-protection protocols to be defined also with the acknowledgment of the Data Protection Officer of each involved institution. Participants' identities will only be shared between the partners where necessary.

Project data will be always kept on password-protected computers. Passwords of encrypted files will be safeguarded. Active files (if anonymized and not including sensitive information) will be stored and shared in VU's SharePoint via Microsoft Teams, set up for the purpose. VU's SharePoint is only accessible through secure credentials and protocols. Network drives will be backed up as part of the partners' IT Service practice. Management of project folders will be the responsibility of each partner.

In all project activities, when stored electronically, identifying information (name, email, gender, job title, organization) will be held separately from main responses, in a password-protected file, except in the case when individuals need to be recontacted based on their response. In these cases, any file containing identifying information would be password protected.

Final data stored in the Zenodo repository is hosted in CERN Data Center, which follows several security measures to ensure that data is stored safely. It is located on CERN premises and all physical access is restricted to limited staff with appropriate training and who have been granted access in line with their professional duties. Servers are managed according to the CERN Security Baseline for Servers, meaning e.g., remote access to our servers is restricted to Zenodo staff with appropriate training, and the operating system and installed applications are kept updated with the latest security patches via our automatic configuration management system Puppet. CERN Security Team runs both host and network-based intrusion detection systems and monitors the traffic flow, pattern, and contents into and out of CERN networks to detect attacks. All access to Zenodo happens over HTTPS, except for static documentation pages which are hosted on GitHub Pages. Zenodo stores user passwords using strong cryptographic password hashing algorithms. Users' access tokens to GitHub and ORCID are stored encrypted and can only be decrypted with the application's secret key.

7. ETHICS

Ethical aspects are discussed in the Ethics Handbook (D1.3), which contains the ethical framework and procedures that will be produced for the project's planning and implementation. All Consortium Partners are committed to complying with relevant international and EU-level fundamental ethical, privacy, and security legislation and regulations. All ethical, legal, and societal issues that arise within the Project will be monitored by FoodCLIC's Ethics Advisory Committee (which includes an external chair with relevant ethics expertise) to ensure that data collection is conducted following (inter)national laws and regulations and that the safety, rights, and wellbeing of participants, particularly deprived and vulnerable groups, will be reviewed.

Regarding data management, efforts will be systematically made to anonymize data to openly share it in the repository. Participation in the project is entirely voluntary and participants will receive the necessary information before they consent to participate, including how their data will be used and processed. Consent forms will include a clause for data sharing and long-term preservation when relevant and appropriate. Personal data will only be collected where necessary and if informed consent has been given. Participants in FoodCLIC events (conferences, workshops, stakeholder forums, etc.) will also receive the necessary information about the handling of their personal data before their consent. Finally, all data and results produced within the FoodCLIC project will be stored in the Zenodo repository.

8. OTHER ISSUES

In addition to all procedures laid out in the DMP and the Grant Agreement, all consortium partners are required to act following any relevant national legislation and other data protection which apply to them. This will be the responsibility of each partner/subcontractor, as they will be best placed to understand the needs dictated by their local/national contexts.

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